

This evaluation rubric was designed by faculty from the Department of Dentistry at Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (Madrid) as a tool to assess preclinical endodontic treatments in multirrooted teeth, within the undergraduate training framework in the subject "Dental Pathology and Therapy II." It is an original instrument that has been used for several years at our university as part of the teaching process, with the aim of promoting structured, objective, and transparent assessment.

Based on its use, we conducted a research study that analyzed the level of agreement between students' self-assessments and the evaluations given by instructors. The study was recently published as a scientific article (DOI: [10.21203/rs.3.rs-5527319/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5527319/v1)).

In order to broaden the scope and utility of this tool, we have translated the rubric into ten languages. We share here the English version with the intention that it may be adopted as-is or serve as a reference for developing similar evaluation systems in other universities worldwide. Our goal is to contribute to more fair, formative, and standardized teaching practices in practical endodontic education.

RUBRIC FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF PRECLINICAL ROOT CANAL TREATMENTS OF MULTIRADICULAR TEETH

Values →		1	2	3	4	5	Student's assessment	Teacher's assessment
Points ↓	ITEMS ↓							
0-1	Radiographic evaluation <i>Mandatory x-rays: 1. Preoperative, 2. WL, 3. Fitting master gutta-percha cone or condensation with accessory cones, 4. Final</i>	More than one mandatory x-rays are missing. All the x-ray films show technical defects and/or processing and/or preservation failures.	One mandatory x-ray is missing. More than one x-ray is missing. More than one x-ray films show technical defects and/or processing and/or preservation failures.	All mandatory x-rays are present. More than one x-ray films show technical defects and/or processing and/or preservation failures.	All mandatory x-rays are present. Only one x-ray film shows technical defects and/or processing and/or preservation failures.	All mandatory x-rays are present and do not show technical defects nor processing or preservation failures.		
		0	0.25	0.5	0.75	1		
0-3	Access cavity	Access cavity preparation is overextended or underextended. All pulp chamber walls and floor are excessively damaged. No root canal has been located. Perforation in furcation or dental crown.	Access cavity preparation is overextended or underextended. Several pulp chamber walls or the floor show excessive damages. Not all root canals are located. Incomplete removal of the roof of the pulp chamber.	Proper access cavity preparation, but one or more pulp chamber walls or the floor have been remarkably damaged. All root canals are located.	Proper access cavity preparation, but one or more pulp chamber walls or the floor show slight damages. All root canals are located.	Proper access cavity preparation. Pulp chamber walls and the floor remain intact. All root canals are located.		
		0	0.75	1.5	2.25	3		
0-3	Instrumentation procedure	Inaccurate WL determination in all root canals (>2mm). Canal anatomy is not preserved and shaping procedure is insufficient or excessive in all canals. At least one procedural error is present: ledge, displacement of apical foramen, fracture of apical foramen, perforation, stripping, zipping, file fracture.	Inaccurate WL determination in one root canal (>2mm). Canal anatomy is not preserved and shaping procedure is insufficient or excessive in more than one canal. At least one procedural error is present: ledge, displacement of apical foramen, fracture of apical foramen, perforation, stripping, zipping, file fracture.	Inaccurate WL determination in one root canal due to severe anatomical alteration. Canal anatomy is not preserved and shaping procedure is insufficient or excessive in one canal. If an accident occurred, proper canal shaping has not been compromised.	Proper WL determination in all root canals. Root canal anatomy is preserved and shaping procedure is adequate in all root canals.	Proper WL determination in all root canals. Root canal anatomy is preserved and shaping procedure is excellent in all canals, with evident progressive taper.		
		0	0.75	1.5	2.25	3		
0-3	Obturation	Inadequate endodontic filling length: excessively sub filled or overfilled in all root canals. Inadequate endodontic filling density (large voids, poor condensation, no adaptation to root canal walls) in all root canals.	Inadequate endodontic filling length: substantially sub filled or overfilled in more than one root canal. Inadequate endodontic filling density (large voids, poor condensation, no adaptation to root canal walls) in more than one root canal.	Inadequate endodontic filling length (slightly sub filled or overfilled) and/or inadequate density (large voids, poor condensation, no adaptation to root canal walls) just in one root canal.	Adequate endodontic filling length in all root canals. Adequate density (no visible voids, good condensation and adaptation to root canal walls) in all root canals.	Adequate endodontic filling length in all root canals. Adequate density (no visible voids, good condensation and adaptation to root canal walls) in all root canals. No radiopaque materials are present in the pulp chamber, root canals are clearly identified and both gutta-percha condensing and cutting are homogeneous.		
		0	0.75	1.5	2.25	3		
TOTAL →								